

Clay Effect on the Morphology and Properties of Poly(methyl methacrylate)/Clay Nanocomposites

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SUMMARY

Three types of clay with different cation exchange capacity (CEC) are applied for the PMMA/clay nanocomposites by solution polymerization. The morphology and properties of the PMMA/clay nanocomposites, such as the thermal, optical, gas barrier, and anti-scratch properties, would be discussed herein the effect of clay with different CEC.

Keywords: solution polymerization; clay; nanocomposite

ABSTRACT

A series of polymer/clay nanocomposites consisting of organic poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) and inorganic montmorillonite (MMT) clay were successfully prepared by in situ free-radical polymerization. Three types of clay have been used as inorganic layered materials in these organic-inorganic hybrid nanocomposites. The properties of these nanocomposites would be compared in this work. The modified clays have been prepared by ionic exchange reaction of cocoamphodipropionate (K2) to increase the surface compatibility between the clay and polymer matrices. The modified clays are characterized by wide angle X-ray diffraction (WAXRD) and FT-infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR). The powdered X-ray diffraction and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) techniques were employed to study the morphology of the PMMA/clay nanocomposites which indicate that the modified clays are dispersed in PMMA matrix to form both exfoliated and intercalated PMMA/modified clay nanocomposites. The thermo-mechanical properties were measured by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). Gas permeability analyzer (GPA) shows the excellent gas barrier property of the nanocomposites which is in good agreement with the morphology. The optical property was measured by UV-Visible spectroscopy which shows that these materials have good optical clarity, UV resistance and anti-scratching property.

Introduction

In recent years, much attention has been paid to polymer-layered silicate nanocomposites, both in academia and industry. Most of them exhibit remarkable improvement in mechanical properties, and barrier properties, thermal stability [1-4]. These unique properties of polymer/clay nanocomposites resulted from high degree of

dispersion of clay in polymer matrix. There are two distinct nanostructures identified in these nanocomposites, intercalated and exfoliated [5]. Exfoliated polymer/silicate nanocomposites are regarded as lightweight and high-performance composites because delaminated clays with high aspect ratio offer large surface areas to polymers.

Recently, radical-initiated MMA polymerization has been applied to prepare PMMA/clay nanocomposites because it is insensitive to water, air, and other impurities. The preparation of PMMA/clay nanocomposites through emulsion [6-8], suspension [8], bulk [9, 10], solution [11] polymerization has been reported in the preparation of exfoliated polymer nanocomposites. Being hydrophilic by nature, pristine montmorillonite is not suitable for direct polymer nanocomposite preparation. Therefore, clays are to be modified by organic modifier containing both hydrophilic and long chain hydrophobic group to increase not only the interlayer spacing, but also the compatibility with the polymer matrices. It is evident that polymer/clay nanocomposites can increase strength and stiffness [12, 13], thermal stability [14, 15], gas barrier property [16,17], clarity[16] and decreased flammability [18,19] with only a small amount of clay.

In our continuous research on the polymer/inorganic layered materials nanocomposites [16, 20-23], we have prepared the PMMA/clay nanocomposites with highly loading of clay by solution polymerization of methyl methacrylate (MMA) with montmorillonite pre-modified with cocoamphodipropionate (K2) and free radical initiator benzoyl peroxide (BPO). We have used three types of montmorillonite clays with different cation exchange capacity (CEC) to prepare the PMMA/clay nanocomposites. We have discussed herein the effect of clay with different cation exchange capacity on the morphology and properties of the PMMA/clay nanocomposites. The morphology of these nanocomposites has been characterized by wide angle X-ray diffraction (WAXRD) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The thermal and gas barrier properties of these nanocomposites have been studied by thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and gas permeability analyzer (GPA). The optical clarity is measured by UV-Vis spectroscopy. From the results, they could show the outstanding properties then previous work.

Experimental Section

Materials

Poly(methyl methacrylate) (Acros, $M_w=350,000$), methyl methacrylate (MMA) (99%, Acros), benzoyl peroxide (Fluka, 97%), 1-Methyl-2-Pyrrolidinone (TEDIA, 95%), tetrahydrofuran for reagent GPC (Mallinckrodt, 99%), acetic acid (SHOWA, 99.7%), toluene (TEDIA, 99.8%), acetone (TEDIA, 95%) were used as received without further purification. The modified agent is cocoamphodipropionate (K2) ($C_{24}H_{44}N_2O_6Na_2$).

Three types of montmorillonite clays i.e. CL42 (PK-802), CL120 (CN-C34), CL88 (CN-C02), CL42 with 116 mequive/100g of cation exchange capacity was supplied by Pailkong Nano Technology. CL120 and CL88 with CEC value of 168 mequive/100g and 200 mequive/100g respectively were supplied by China Glaze Co.

Modification of MMT

The organic clay was prepared by cation exchange reaction between the sodium cation of the MMT and protonized K2. Typically, 3g of MMT was suspended in 90mL

distilled water and stirred at room temperature overnight. Then clay suspensions were dropwise added into the soluble K2 slowly, followed by the addition of 1M acetic acid aqueous solution to adjust the pH value to about 4-5. The mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature. The organic modified clay was separated by ultracentrifugation (9000 rpm, 30 min) and the washing step were repeated at least three times.

Preparation of the PMMA/Clay Nanocomposites

The typical procedure for preparation of PMMA/clay nanocomposites with 1wt% clay loading, first, an appropriate amount modified clay (0.1g) was suspended into 30mL of toluene under magnetic stirring overnight at room temperature. 9.9g of methacrylate monomer and 0.097g of benzoyl peroxide initiator were added to this solution. Under magnetic stirring, the solution was stirred for 5h at 75°C in a nitrogen atmosphere and the final product was precipitated in 800mL of n-hexane. The product was dissolved in 30mL of toluene and re-precipitation process was repeated to obtain more pure nanocomposites. The PMMA/clay nanocomposites were dried at 80°C in a vacuum for 5h.

Preparation of the PMMA/Clay Thin Film

To enhance the mechanical strength of thin film, the commercial PMMA with high molecular weight ($M_w=350,000$) was blended into the casting solution for film formation. The as-synthesized PMMA/clay nanocomposites (0.5g) blended with 0.5g of commercialized PMMA were dissolved in 9.5g NMP under magnetic stirring overnight at room temperature. The solution was cast onto a glass plate and then to evaporate at 60°C under a hood for 24h.

Characterization

Wide angle X-ray diffraction (WAXRD) was carried out with a PANalytical PW3040/60 X'Pert Pro using Cu radiation ($\lambda=1.54\text{\AA}$) with the step size of 0.02° and time per step 16. The scanning angle ranges were 2 θ from 1.5-65° (MMT) or 2-30° (nanocomposites). Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra were measured on pressed KBr pellets with a Jasco FT/IR-460 Plus spectrometer. The morphology of the clay in the hybrids was observed on a transmission electron microscope (TEM) (JEM2010, 200KV, and JEOL). The samples with a thickness of 70 nm were prepared by using Leica Ultracut-UCT. The nanocomposites were extracted by acetone using a Soxhlet extractor to obtain the clay freed polymer. The molecular weight of the pure PMMA and the extracted polymer in the PMMA/clay nanocomposites were determined by gel permeation chromatography (GPC) (Waters GPC-150CV) analysis with THF as the eluent.

The glass transition temperature (T_g) was determined by using a TAQ10 differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) at a heating rate of 10°C/min. The thermal decomposition temperature was determined by thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA)(SII TG/DTA6200); the experiment was carried out from 40 to 900°C at a scanning rate of 20°C/min. The gas permeability analyzer (GPA) was performed with Yanco (GTR-31) to permeate experiment of oxygen gas. UV/Visible transmission spectra were obtained with a Cary-100 UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The anti-scratch property was measured according to ASTM D 3363 method.

Results and Discussion

Characterization of K2-Modified MMT

In WAXRD patterns of three types of pure and modified clays are shown in Figure 1(a), (b), and (c). The basal reflection characteristic of MMT clay was $2\theta=7.13^\circ$ (basal spacing=1.24nm) for CL42, $2\theta=5.95^\circ$ (basal spacing=1.48nm) for CL120 and $2\theta=5.79^\circ$ (basal spacing=1.53nm) for CL88. For modified MMT, the d-spacing increased to 4.10nm for CL42, 4.09nm for CL120 and 4.05nm for CL88. The d-spacing of modified clay depends on the different orientation of the modified agents and molecular sizes. The increased d-spacing is due to the fact that Na^+ ions presented in the layers are exchanged by the modifier. Figure 2 shows the FT-IR spectra of (a) the pure CL120 (b) modified CL120-K2, and (c) PMMA/CL120-K2 3% nanocomposites. In the FT-IR spectrum of pure CL120 (Figure 2a), the bands appeared at 1,035, 540, and 460 cm^{-1} is due to stretching frequency of Si-O, Al-O and Mg-O, respectively of pure MMT-clay [24]. In the spectrum of the modified CL120-K2 (Figure 2b), the C-H stretching bands are found at 2855 and 2920 cm^{-1} , confirming the presence of ethyl group in the layers of the clay. The other clays have the same types of bands are also observed in the FT-IR spectra.

Figure 1. Wide-angle X-ray diffraction patterns of (a) pure CL42 and modified CL42-K2 (b) pure CL120 and modified CL120-K2 (c) pure CL88 and modified CL88-K2.

Figure 2. FT-IR of (a) the pure CL120 (b) modified CL120-K2, and (c) PMMA/CL120-K2 3% nanocomposites.

Morphology of the PMMA/Clay Nanocomposites

Clays with different weight percent loading were incorporated into the PMMA matrix to form the well-dispersed nanocomposites. Figure 3 shows WAXRD patterns of a series of PMMA/clay nanocomposites. There was no diffraction peak at $2\theta=2-10^\circ$ for PMMA/clay nanocomposites with 1, 3, and 5 wt% clay loading. It might indicate that the layered materials are dispersed well into the PMMA matrices. To further investigate the clay dispersion in the polymer matrix, TEM analysis was performed, as shown in Figure 4(a),(b). PMMA/CL42-K2 3 and 5 wt% display almost intercalated and partly exfoliated morphology. Figure 4(a),(b) show PMMA/CL120-K2 and PMMA/CL88-K2 with 3 and 5 wt% display almost exfoliated morphology.

Figure 3. Wide-angle X-ray diffraction patterns of (a) PMMA/CL42-K2 nanocomposites (b) PMMA/CL120-K2 nanocomposites (c) PMMA/CL88-K2 nanocomposites with MMT content of 1, 3, 5 wt%.

Figure 4. TEM images of (a) PMMA/clay nanocomposites containing 3 wt% clay at 50K (b) PMMA/clay nanocomposites containing 5 wt% clay at 50K.

Table 1. Relationship of the Composition of PMMA/clay Nanocomposites Prepared by Solution Polymerization with the Thermal Stability, Molecular weight, and Gas Barrier.

sample	Thermal properties		Molecular Weight ^c			Gas Barrier ^d
	T _d (°C) ^a	T _g (°C) ^b	Mn	Mw	PDI	O ₂ (barrer)
Pure PMMA	240	96	22400	46800	2.09	0.725
PMMA/CL42-K2 1%	266	99	20700	43300	2.09	0.509
PMMA/CL42-K2 3%	284	103	19800	40500	2.05	0.575
PMMA/CL42-K2 5%	288	118	18700	37200	1.99	0.604
PMMA/CL120-K2 1%	273	107	18300	37000	2.02	0.429
PMMA/CL120-K2 3%	287	119	17900	36500	2.04	0.331
PMMA/CL120-K2 5%	296	122	18600	30600	1.65	0.348
PMMA/CL88-K2 1%	271	114	22400	37100	1.66	0.535
PMMA/CL88-K2 3%	285	114	18200	36900	2.02	0.525
PMMA/CL88-K2 5%	295	116	15900	32700	2.16	0.648

^aAs measured by TGA. T_d was the temperature value at 5% weight loss. ^bAs measured by DSC. ^cAs measured by GPC. ^dAs measured by GPA.

Characterization of PMMA/Clay Nanocomposites

In Figure 2(c) of PMMA/clay nanocomposites shows a distinct absorption at 1730 cm⁻¹ (C=O stretching) and 1300-1100 cm⁻¹ (C-O stretching), which are the characteristic bands of PMMA. Figure 5 shows the TGA of powder PMMA/clay nanocomposites. The decomposition temperature (T_d) of 5% weight loss data for pure PMMA and PMMA/clay nanocomposites with different wt% of clay loading are listed in Table 1a. Evidently, T_d of the PMMA/clay nanocomposites materials prepared with both approaches shift toward a higher temperature range than that of pure PMMA, and this confirmed the enhancement of the thermal stability of the intercalated and exfoliated composites. However, the exfoliated composite (e.g. PMMA/CL120-K2 5%) exhibited higher thermal stability enhancement than the intercalated composite (e.g. PMMA/CL42-K2 5%) with the same clay loading. Furthermore, DSC traces of the pure PMMA and PMMA/clay nanocomposites materials are shown in Figure 6. T_g of the composites increased with an increasing concentration of clay platelets in the polymer framework, as shown in Table 1b. Such increase in T_g is generally attributed to restricted segmental motion near the interface of the inorganic-organic nanocomposites. The exfoliated composite (e.g. PMMA/CL120-K2 5%) exhibited higher T_g, which results from strong interaction between the clay layers and the PMMA chain.

Figure 5. TGA curves of (a) PMMA/CL42-K2 nanocomposites (b) PMMA/CL120-K2 nanocomposites (c) PMMA/CL88-K2 nanocomposites.

Figure 6. DSC curves of (a) PMMA/CL42-K2 nanocomposites (b) PMMA/CL120-K2 nanocomposites (c) PMMA/CL88-K2 nanocomposites.

Optical Clarity of PMMA/Clay Nanocomposites

Figure 7 shows the UV-visible transmission spectra of the PMMA/clay nanocomposite membranes ($100 \pm 15 \mu\text{m}$) with different clay contents. The PMMA/clay nanocomposites show a slight decline in transmission in the visible light region with the increase of the clay content, the nanocomposite can still retain a high optical transmission of approximately 85%. The transparency is shown in Figure 8 which indicates that the material has good optical property.

Barrier-Gas Property of PMMA/Clay Nanocomposites

The gas permeability of the pure PMMA and a series of PMMA/clay nanocomposite membranes was determined with Yanco GTR-10 gas permeability analyzer. The gas permeability was calculated according to the following equation:

$$P = \frac{q \times k' \times l}{a \times t \times p} \left(\frac{\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{cm}}{\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{sec} \cdot \text{cmHg}} \right)$$

Where q is the permeation amount; k' is the coefficient; l is the thickness; p is the pressure; a is the permeation area; t is the measurement time, respectively.

Gas permeability data are summarized in Table 1d. In addition, the O_2 permeability of PMMA/CL120-K2 5% (0.348 barrer) was significantly lower than that of PMMA/CL42-K2 5% (0.604 barrer). This may be explained considering the different dispersion of two types of clay. The exfoliated composite of PMMA/CL120-K2 5%, gas has to pass the longer path and needs more time. The gas barrier property is thus improved.

Figure 7. UV-vis transmission spectra of (a) PMMA/CL42-K2 nanocomposites (b) PMMA/CL120-K2 nanocomposites (c) PMMA/CL88-K2 nanocomposites.

Figure 8. Optical transparency of PMMA/clay nanocomposites.

Anti-Scratch Property of PMMA/Clay Nanocomposites

Pencil (Eagle Turquoise-T 2375) hardness test is a simple and effective technique to evaluate the anti-scratch property of the material. The pencil lead, prepared beforehand by rubbing it on fine abrasive paper (400), is maintained at an angle of 45° and pushed with uniform force with 1.5 kg onto the sample, leaving either a superficial trace or causing destruction down to the substrate. Hardness is compared with the pure PMMA polymer and data are listed in Table 2. It has been observed that the hardness of PMMA/CL120-K2 nanocomposites and PMMA/CL88-K2 nanocomposites with 3 wt% loading of clay is 3H. Exfoliated nature of the nanocomposites may be the reason for increasing the surface hardness.

Table 2. Anti-scratch data of PMMA/clay nanocomposites.

Clay \ Loading	Pure PMMA Hardness: H		
	1%	3%	5%
CL42-K2	3H	2H	2H
CL120-K2	2H	3H	2H
CL88-K2	2H	3H	2H

Conclusions

Three clays are used to compare the thermal, optical, gas barrier, and anti-scratch properties. The incorporation of a small amount of clay into the PMMA matrix results in obvious enhancement in the thermal properties of PMMA. It has been observed that the CL120 with suitable CEC has the excellent thermal, gas barrier, and anti-scratch properties with 5 wt% of clay is incorporated in the PMMA matrices due to exfoliated morphology. Optical clarity is also excellent in these PMMA/clay nanocomposites.

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